

DEVELOPING STRATEGIC PLAN OF ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF IRAN JUDO FEDERATION BASED ON SWOT ANALYSIS

Mohammad Hami^{1*}. Fahimeh Mohammad Hassan²

¹ Associate Professor, Department of Sports Management, Islamic Azad University, Sari Branch, Sari, Iran, email: mohammadhami@yahoo.com

² Assistant Professor in Sports Management, Sport Sciences research Institute of Iran, email: f.mohammadhassan@gmail.com

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

The present research aims to investigate strategic situation of Islamic Republic of Iran Judo Federation and developing appropriate strategies in order to promote Judo. This is a descriptive research of the type of strategic studies that has been carried out quantitatively and qualitatively, and the required data was collected through the researcher's made questionnaire. Considering the purpose and method of the research and the limited population, the opinions of Judo sports experts were collected using total population sampling which finally 70 questionnaires were collected. 10 sports management professors confirmed the face and content validity of the questionnaire and its reliability was obtained 0.77 through Cronbach's coefficient, which finally resulted in the number of 25 weaknesses, 21 strengths, 20 opportunities, 19 threats, 8 missions, 6 core values, and 12 strategies. In general, four vision and five strategic goals were identified. To analyze data, in addition to the descriptive indices of the Kolmogorov Smirnov tests to determine the normality of the data distribution, the one-sample t-test, the binomial test to examine the variables, and the Friedman test to prioritize the components, the external and internal evaluation matrix and quantitative strategic planning matrix (QSPM) has also been used. Due to the findings of the research: the lack of cheap access for everyone to sports facilities with an average rating of 14.62 as the most important weakness and the existence of a young and adolescent community with an average rating of 13.09 was identified as the most important strength. Also emphasis of religious teachings in dealing with the issue of sports with an average rank of 12.59 was identified as the most important opportunity and the economic problems of the people with an average of 11.81 was determined as the most important threat to the development of the sport of Judo around Iran.

Moreover, planning for the development of judo sport with an average of 4.93 was identified as the most important mission statement, and respecting the culture and honoring the personality of employees and clients of the federation with an average of 3.64 was considered as the most important core value statement and easy access to judo sport with an average of 6.92 was considered as the most important vision of the Iran Judo federation. Additionally, training of skilled and capable forces with an average rating of 3.12 is the most important strategic goal of the development of judo sport in Iran. The evaluation matrix of internal factors showed that the strengths will overcome its weaknesses to some extent and the evaluation matrix of external factors showed that the position of the development strategy of Iran's judo sport is in the 775 region. According to these results, it should be acknowledged that the conditions indicate the use of conservative strategies.

Keywords: Strategic Plan, Judo Sport, Sport Development in Iran, SWOT

1. INTRODUCTION

The popularity of judo all around the world, made judo one of the most prominent Olympic games. Currently, more than 187 national federations are members of the International Judo Federation. Judo is one of the most practiced sports in the world with more than 20 million judokas. The sport of judo and the importance of investing in it has become one of the challenges of the governments in the third millennium, so that the great benefits of the championship sport have encouraged the policy makers and their development in order to gain more profit for themselves.

In general, the sport of judo is very important throughout life and it is appropriate solution to spend free time. So that it has a great impact on the physical and mental health of people (Kherand, 2015). The name Judo was chosen because it means the "gentle or yielding way". It was introduced into the Olympic Games in 1964 and is practiced by millions of people throughout the world today. It is best known for its spectacular throwing techniques but also involves considerable grappling on the ground utilizing specialized pins, control holds, arm locks, and Judo choking techniques. It emphasizes safety, and full physical activity for top conditioning. It is learned on special mats for comfort and safety.

The principles of Judo, such as "Maximum Efficiency" and "Mutual Welfare and Benefit", can also be used in our dealings with others in life. The ultimate goal is to develop oneself to the maximum extent possible, always striving for perfection, so that you can contribute something of value to the world. Many adverse effects of the social environment, economy, family situation, heredity and the like are reduced or even completely eliminated through exercise (Barrie Houliham & Anta White, 2012). The obvious benefits of participating in judo activities can be counted in four points including increase of health level, promotion of physical fitness, weight loss, and develop of physical strength.

Judo is a physical sport for those who want to have a fit body. By practicing, one can increase both strength and flexibility. While practicing judo skills, the body becomes stronger and it also strengthens the cardiovascular system. Judokas can focus faster than others and increase their level of concentration. This ability is not only used when practicing judo, but also makes the judo player perform better at work. During judo training, judo players learn how to cope under pressure and keep calm, this feature can help in anything in life such as calming a person when facing problems in his life. When the judoka follows the judo sports recommendations in his daily life and applies them, he will enjoy the benefits of judo sports in all respects and will have a peaceful life. The advantages of judo are infinite, the more you learn, the more you feel its advantages (Javadipour, 2020).

In our today's life, it is definitely clear that the structure of organizations has become so complicated that they cannot continue their existence without meticulous planning. sports organizations are not excluded from this category, planning in judo federation is considered as the most important management task, just like any other organization. In fact, planning in judo means that the goals of all activities and group efforts are determined and how to achieve those goals is planned (Mozafari, 2018). Judo Federation, like any other system, needs the development of macro-goals, strategies and action plans so that while knowing the direction of movement, it can avoid any rework, idleness and waste of its financial, human, physical and informational resources. Strategic planning is a process in order to equip the federation's resources and unify its efforts to achieve its mission and long-term goals, taking into account the internal and external capabilities and limitations of each organization. In this process, internal strengths and weaknesses, external opportunities and threats (SWOT) are analyzed and identified, and according to the mission of the organization, long-term goals are formulated for it, and to achieve these goals, the final strategy is chosen from among the strategic options, which will lead the organization by focusing on the strengths and taking advantage of the opportunities, and avoiding the threats (Alvani, 2005).

Examining the state of judo in some countries of Australia, Germany, Japan, France, Denmark, Brazil and Russia shows that the regular program for the growth and development of judo in these countries has more than 60 years history. Several factors play a role in this success, first of all, we can mention the growth of the judo sports program in the framework of the national programs of these countries and the effective support of the governments for these programs (Javadipour, 2020). Considering all mentioned aspects, the researcher aims to investigate strategic situation of Islamic Republic of Iran Judo Federation in order to develop appropriate strategies for promotion of Judo.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method of this research is descriptive of the type of strategic studies that have been carried out quantitatively and qualitatively. Then, the weight and intensity of each of the factors of the strategic position

of judo is known from the SWOT profile through valuation. In order to obtain the required data for the research, first a questionnaire was designed to determine the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats and existing goals for the development of the Judo Federation and sent to all sports experts. After defining the SWOT components, a questionnaire was designed and sent to the experts.

Finally, after a complete consensus about the research variables, "31 variables related to weaknesses and 24 variables related to strengths, 25 variables related to opportunities and 24 variables related to threats, 5 variables related to missions, 7 variables related to core values, 12 variables related to judo sports strategies, 4 variables related to the vision and 7 variables related to the criteria of strategic goals" of Judo Federation were identified by judo experts. The number of samples reached 15 until the model reached the stage of construction and saturation.

In the quantitative part, the variables in the internal and external environments of the strategic management of Judo Federation were evaluated, important and less important factors were identified and prioritized.

IFE and EFE matrices were used to evaluate internal and external strategic factors. The Internal Factors Evaluation Matrix or IFE is a tool for examining internal factors and actually evaluates the strengths and weaknesses of organizational units. The EFE external factors evaluation matrix is a tool for analyzing how the managers of the organization respond and face the opportunities and threats outside the organization.

In the next step, each factor was assigned a weight coefficient between zero (unimportant) and one (very important).

Normalization is used for weighting. The coefficients given to each factor indicate its relative importance in success. Regardless of whether the factor in question is considered an internal strength or weakness. The highest coefficient is given to the factor that has the greatest effect on the performance of the organization. Then, the status of each factor is determined with a score between 1 and 4 (1 = weak, 2 = average, 3 = above average, 4 = very good), which is called the status que score.

If the management of the organization seeks to reduce the weaknesses or threats, it will get a high score for the weakness or threat, and on the contrary, if the strengths and opportunities are not managed well, it will receive a low score. Therefore, the weighted score of each factor is calculated, for this purpose, the score of each row of internal and external factors of the organization is multiplied by the normalized weight and inserted in a new column. In this step, the sum of weighted points is calculated. If the final score of the matrix of internal factors is less than 2.5. This means that the development of the Judo Federation is weak in terms of internal factors.

Also, if the final score of the matrix of external factors of the Judo Federation is weak in terms of internal factors, also if the final score of the matrix of external factors of the weighted development of the Judo Federation is less than 2.5, it is confirmed that the weighted development of the Judo Federation regarding the use of opportunities and dealing with threats does not work well.

The research population was include of sports management professors, heads of provincial boards of Judo federation, stakeholders and champions in Judo as well as Judo federation experts.

3. FINDINGS

After the internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) were identified, the priority factors were placed in a column of the matrix and scored using special coefficients and ranks to finally determine that the strategic development plan of the Judo Federation in the future they wants to plan for, will have more strengths or face more weaknesses.

The below table contains the evaluation matrix of internal factors:

According to the fact that the final score of the Judo Federation's development in this matrix was calculated equal to 2.266, it is concluded that the strengths of the Judo Federation will overcome its weaknesses to some extent.

Table 1. Evaluation matrix of the internal development factors of the Judo Federation

Strengths	Weight	Rating	R × W
The Support of Judo Federation president from Judo	0.02	3.7	0.074
Various local attractions for judo competitions	0.024	3.2	0.077

Strengths	Weight	Rating)R × W(
Interest of the community of youth and teenagers in the sport of judo	0.024	3.66	0.087
Social security to participate in judo sports programs	0.02	3.83	0.076
Existence of proficient experts in Judo	0.021	3.33	0.069
Acceptable contribution of Judo Coach around the country	0.021	3.58	0.075
People's interest in judo athletes and champions	0.024	3.33	0.079
Holding proper number of competitions in the field of judo sport by provincial boards	0.024	3.58	0.085
Individual and organizational motivations and passion suitable for the development and generalization of judo sport	0.024	3.16	0.075
Membership in the International and Asian Judo Association	0.021	3.33	0.069
Appropriate access and benefit from the capacities and cooperation - active participation of governmental and non-governmental departments, organizations and institutions.	0.024	3.66	0.087
Existence of championship and wellness bases	0.02	3.16	0.063
Availability of appropriate sports conditions	0.021	3.19	0.066
Appropriate performance of provincial boards	0.02	3.66	0.073
The potential of holding judo sports events	0.024	3.83	0.091
Participation of the private sector in holding judo related events	0.021	3.33	0.069
Feeling the free time of youth and teenagers throughout the year	0.027	3.16	0.085
Weaknesses	Weight	Rating)R × W(
Lack of short-term planning in the Judo Federation	0.017	1.14	0/019
The lack of attention of the managers of sports and youth general administration to judo	0.015	1.6	0/027
Lack of long-term plans in the Judo Federation	0.022	1.71	0/034
Lack of facilities and infrastructure for Judo sport in the provinces in terms of quantity	0.023	1.28	0/029
Lack of integrated information system (system of collection, processing...) in the Judo Federation	0.02	1.28	0/028
The lack of quality of facilities and equipment of judo sports championship bases in provinces	0.02	1.42	0/028
Not holding scientific-specialized seminars in the field of judo	0.02	1.71	0/034
Lack of advertisement of judo sport by media	0.02	1/42	0/028
Lack of facilities and equipment for judo sports in the provinces in terms of quality	0.02	1/14	0/023

Strengths	Weight	Rating)R × W(
Absence of various websites regarding cultural-sports issues	0.018	1	0/018
Not to publish information related to sports events and their side ceremonies before holding competitions	0.02	1/28	0/025
Weakness in performance of provincial boards	0.021	1	0/021
Absence of necessary instructions for performing judo	0.021	1/14	0/024
Lack of attention to judo for the disabled	0.018	1/28	0/023
Lack of attention to judo for the women	0.02	1/42	0/028
Lack of attention to judo for the rurals	0.018	1/71	0/03
Not to apply the academic potential of the country on the promotion of Judo	0.023	1	0/23
Weakness of the communication and information system in the Judo Federation	0.02	1/28	0/025
Total	1		2.266

The final score of the development of the Judo Federation was calculated as 2.439 in the evaluation matrix of external factors. It could be concluded that the opportunities for the development of Judo Federation will overcome its threats to some extent.

Table 2. Evaluation matrix of the external development factors of the Judo Federation

Opportunities	Weight	Rating)R × W(
Emphasis of religious orders in exercising	0/028	3	0/08
Increase of peoples interest to Judo events	0/028	4	0/11
Easy access to appropriate and standard communication methods	0/032	3/7	0/12
The acceptability of judo for the general public	0/031	3/8	0/12
Good performance of sports media in provinces	0/032	4	0/13
Holding various coaching and refereeing courses	0/031	4	0/12
Attractive sightseeing around clubs	0/027	3/5	0/09
Support and supervision of governmental officials from Judo	0/031	3/5	0/11
spirit of ethnic unity of the people of the provinces in the field of judo	0/028	3/5	0/1
Spreading out the principles of Islamic philosophy and Iranian religion through the development of judo sport	0/024	3/5	0/08
Optimal weather conditions (need for covered venues) of the provinces in holding judo activities	0/028	4	0/11
radio and television programs in the provinces about the education and promotion of judo	0/035	3/5	0/13

Opportunities	Weight	Rating)R × W(
Awareness of people about Judo as martial art	0/024	3	0/07
encouraging and persuading people to judo by press	0/027	3/5	0/09
The society's positive attitude towards sports activities as a psychological-social-moral constructive factor	0/025	3/5	0/087
Activity of popular institutions and religious centers in the expansion of Judo	0/031	3/5	0/11
Threats	Weight	Rating)R × W(
High unemployment rate of Judo coaches	0/021	1/5	0/04
Increase in the number of drug addicts	0/021	2	0/2
Increase in types of pollution	0/035	1/7	0/06
Increase in the price of judo sports equipment and supplies	0/035	1/5	0/052
Involvement of Judo with politics	0/035	1/5	0/052
Increasing the maintenance costs of indoor halls	0/033	1	0/033
People's mechanical and passive life style	0/031	2	0/06
Changing the structure of cities and destroying indoor places	0/028	1/5	0/04
The existence of some religious-social prejudices	0/032	2	0/06
Lack of effective supervision on the development process of judo sport	0/026	2	0/05
Lack of motivation for the private sector to invest in developing places and promoting judo sports activities	0/028	1/5	0/04
Absence of macro and strategic policies in the country	0/028	1/5	0/04
cultural differences in the development of judo sport	0/035	1	0/035
Unwanted social and behavioral abnormalities in the sports environment	0/032	2	0/06
Lack of coherent planning system to attract non-governmental financial and economic resources	0/035	2	0/07
Lack of sufficient recognition of the international capabilities of judo sport	0/035	2	0/07
Total	1		2/439

3.1. Internal and External Analysis and Determining the Main Strategy

The final score of the evaluation matrix of internal and external factors determined that the position of the development strategy of the Judo Federation is in the WO region (according to these results, it should be acknowledged that these conditions indicate the use of conservative strategies and maintaining the status quo and close to the offensive area.

In order to access this situation, the researcher proceeded to compile the matrix and plan the development strategy of the Judo Federation. This state shows a focus on conservative strategies in this field. It is worth mentioning that conservative strategies include: developing people's easy access to judo sport, expanding partnership with scientific institutions for the development of judo sport and developing the infrastructure of judo sport.

Figure1. Final Score of IFE-EFE & determining organizational strategy

Prioritization of conservative WO strategies based on QSPM matrix:

Considering the priority of the conservative WO strategies obtained in the internal and external matrix, at this stage, in order to analyze the results, the QSPM strategic planning matrix is presented for WO strategies.

Based on this, the WO strategy has been prioritized according to the table below.

1. Expansion of partnership with scientific institutions for the development of judo sport
2. Developing people's easy access to judo
3. Development of Judo sports infrastructure

Table 3. QSPM matrix for prioritizing conservative development strategies of Judo Federation

QSPM Matrix for prioritizing conservative Strategies							
Strategy		WO1		WO2		WO3	
Component	Relative coefficient	Rating	Total Weight	Rating	Total Weight	Rating	Total Weight
W1	0/019	4	0/076	3	0/057	3	0/057
W2	0/027	4	0/108	2	0/054	3	0/081
W3	0/034	2	0/068	3	0/102	4	0/136
W4	0/029	3	0/087	4	0/116	3	0/087
W5	0/028	2	0/056	3	0/084	1	0/028
W6	0/028	4	0/122	4	0/112	2	0/056
W7	0/034	4	0/136	1	0/034	3	0/102
W8	0/028	2	0/056	2	0/056	1	0/028
W9	0/023	4	0/092	2	0/046	2	0/046
W10	0/018	4	0/072	2	0/036	4	0/072
W11	0/025	3	0/075	3	0/075	4	0/1
W12	0/018	2	0/036	2	0/036	3	0/054
W13	0/021	1	0/021	4	0/084	2	0/042
W14	0/028	3	0/084	1	0/028	4	0/112
W15	0/024	2	0/048	3	0/072	2	0/048
W16	0/025	2	0/05	2	0/05	4	0/1
W17	0/023	3	0/069	3	0/069	1	0/023

W18	0/028	4	0/0112	2	0/056	3	0/084
W19	0/03	1	0/03	4	0/12	1	0/03
W20	0/024	4	0/096	2	0/048	2	0/048
W21	0/03	1	0/03	3	0/09	4	0/12
W22	0/031	3	0/093	4	0/0124	1	0/031
W23	0/025	2	0/05	3	0/075	3	0/075
W24	0/023	3	0/069	3	0/069	4	0/092
W25	0/025	4	0/01	2	0/05	4	0/1
O1	0/08	2	0/16	1	0/08	3	0/24
O2	0/11	3	0/33	2	0/22	3	0/33
O3	0/12	3	0/36	3	0/36	1	0/12
O4	0/12	4	0/48	3	0/36	2	0/24
O5	0/13	2	0/26	4	0/52	3	0/39
O6	0/12	3	0/36	2	0/24	2	0/24
O7	0/09	2	0/18	2	02/18	3	0/27
O8	0/011	2	0/22	3	0/33	1	0/11
O9	0/1	3	0/3	4	0/4	2	0/2
O10	0/08	2	0/16	2	0/16	3	0/24
O11	0/11	4	0/44	4	0/44	3	0/33
O12	0/9	2	0/18	1	0/9	3	0/27
O13	0/13	1	0/13	2	0/26	3	0/39
O14	0/07	2	0/14	3	0/21	1	0/07
O15	0/09	3	0/27	1	0/09	2	0/18
O16	0/087	2	0/174	3	0/261	4	0/348
O17	0/11	3	0/076	2	0/22	2	0/22
Total			6/046		6/974		5/94

4.DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION

-What are the weaknesses of the Judo Federation's development and its priority?

Based on the findings of this research, in the factors related to the weaknesses of the development of judo sport, the significance level of $P < 0.01$ is acceptable according to the experts. In this regard, the results of the Friedman test regarding the weaknesses in the development of judo sport in the Judo Federation were also significant with a chi-square of 64.918 and a degree of freedom of 22 ($P < 0.01$). These results show that the criterion of not having cheap access to sports venues and facilities for everyone has the highest priority with an average rating of 14.62, and the lowest priority belongs to the lack of necessary instructions for judo with an average rating of 8.99, which is in line with the findings of Ghanbari (2012), Ghofrani et al. (2007).

Weaknesses are activities in which the organization does not perform well, or resources that it should have but does not have. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt strategies to transform these strengths based on environmental opportunities and threats. The results of the research showed that the Judo Federation has some weaknesses. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt strategies to turn these weaknesses into strengths based on the opportunities and environmental threats of judo sport. Based on the research, lack of cheap access to sports venues and facilities for everyone was recognized as the most important weakness of judo sport. Therefore, establishing judo venues and providing the necessary facilities could be a great step.

In this regard, it could be mentioned that one of the problems that is the lack of people's interest in participating in sports activities, is partly dependent on public access, due to the lack of sports facilities.

Planning for sports should be done according to the needs of this large group, adapting the existing facilities to their needs or creating new possibilities for their needs. Also, sports organizations should put the development of sports venues and facilities in their priority programs, with detailed knowledge of the impact of sports and well-equipped stadiums and build many sports complexes and guide a large number of citizens and those interested in judo to sports.

-What are the strenghts of the Judo Federation's development and its priority?

The results of the Friedman test regarding the criteria of the strenghts in the development of the Judo Federation were significant with a chi-square of 99.915 and a degree of freedom of 20 ($P < 0.01$). In this study, the criterion of the presence of the youth community in the sport of Judo with an average rank of 13.09, is the highest priority and the criterion of the good connections and membership in "The Association

For International Sport for All" (TAFISA) and the "Asian Sports for All Association" (ASFAA) with an average rank 7/62 has the lowest priority. The results are in line with the findings of Khosravizadeh (2007), Yetz (2001), Ghofrani (2008). Strengths are activities in which the organization performs well or resources that are under the control of the organization. Such forces can help to fulfill its mission. Provided that they are in line with minimizing weaknesses and reducing the effects of threats and making the most use of opportunities. Therefore, it is appropriate to try to maintain and strengthen these strengths.

According to the statistics of the National Youth Organization, about 68% of the country's population is made up of young people and teenagers, and more than 60% of young people have the possibility of taking risks, which shows the weakness of the economic, social and cultural structures of the country. Therefore, sports provides a platform for presenting the personal capabilities of young people. This feature of sports is very useful especially for those young people who do not have the opportunity to show their abilities in other situations of their lives.

After all, exercise provides many healthy alternatives to harmful activities such as drug use and crime. Sport increases economic development by providing cheap ways to improve employment, especially among young people. By teaching basic and necessary skills for work and economic activities, sports provides constructive activities for young people, through which the amount of social crimes and abnormal social behaviors is reduced. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to young people and teenagers due to their high potential in the Judo Federation, considering the results obtained. In this way, it is suggested that the authorities support this group and expand the necessary facilities for the development of judo.

-What are the opportunities of the Judo Federation's development and its priority?

Based on the findings of this research, in the factors related to the opportunities of the Judo Federation development, the significance level of $P < 0.01$ is acceptable from the experts' point of view. In this regard, the results of the Friedman test regarding the criteria of Judo sports development opportunities of the Judo Federation were also significant with a chi-square of 57.561 and a degree of freedom of 19. ($P > 0.01$). These results show the greater priority of emphasis of religious orders in exercising with an average of 12.59 and the least importance related to the existence of the spirit of ethnic unity of the people of the provinces in the field of judo with an average rating of 9.41. The results are consistent with the findings of Ghanbari (2012) and Ghofrani (2007) and Gouderzi et al. (2021).

If the officials and managers of the Judo Federation, by bringing the social sphere closer to the religious sphere, define and implement recreation and sports as the main basis of health and vitality within the framework of custom and culture of the people, they can increase the development of the mental health of the society and cause the development of judo sport. Therefore, it is necessary for the officials of the federation to pay special attention to the spiritual characteristics of this discipline and to take advantage of this capacity and to use the scientific products of the physical training and sports science centers in order to promote Judo around the country.

-What are the threats of the Judo Federation's development and its priority?

Based on the findings of this research, in the factors related to the threats to the development of judo sport, the significance level of $P < 0.01$ is acceptable according to the experts. In this regard, the results of the Friedman test regarding the criteria of physical education and sports science approaches were also significant with a chi-square of 34.691 and a degree of freedom of 18 ($P < 0.05$). These results indicate the higher priority of the measure of people's economic problems with an average of 11.81 and the lower priority of the unwanted social and behavioral abnormalities in the sports environment with an average of 8.79. The results are in line with the findings of Talab (2021), Ghanbari (2012), Khaki et al. (2019), Ghofrani (2007).

Economic challenges, especially in the production and income sector, are among the important issues that humans always struggle with. More production provides the possibility of improving life, benefiting from better material, cultural and social conditions and having more effective infrastructure facilities. The poverty and wealth of any country depends on the per capita production capacity of economic systems in its various sectors. Economic status has an impact on various aspects of life, including the choice of type and amount of physical activities. The presence of certain classes in sports activities is affected by their economic status, and a person's behavior and attitude regarding health and having a healthy body depends on his economic-social status.

Farrell et al. (2013) showed in their research that a high level of physical inactivity is related to important dimensions of economic status. Education, family income and local deprivations were all independently and ethnically related to lack of physical activities and control of access to sports facilities and recreational facilities. So there was a big socio-economic gradient even for low-cost activities like walking.

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The results of this research show that judo faces such threats in different areas; which can create major challenges if it does not find ways to deal with them. Therefore, managers should deal with them actively and dynamically. It seems it would be applicable to use the strategy of creating motivational mechanisms to attract financial sponsors - expanding the financial facilities of the sports industry - promoting the culture of spending on sports and reducing the entrance fees related to the use of sports facilities and the support of the officials and sports managers of the Judo Federation.

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